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Role of Foreign Remittance in Rural Poverty Reduction

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ABSTRACT

There has been a rapid increase in remittance inflows in Nepal since the last decade. Contribution of remittance to foreign exchange earning exceeds export, foreign direct investment (FDI) and foreign aid and economic growth is also improving simultaneously. The practice of remitting money by foreign workers to the home country has a significant history in Nepal. The ability to make these remittances allowed the remitter's families to buy land, educate their children and improve their standard of living and that of their village as a whole. The increased global integration and the enhancement in communication technology have facilitated migration of youths from Nepal to foreign countries; as a result, the flow of remittances started growing at a higher pace from gulf and other countries to Nepal. Consequently, remittance has become an important contributor to Nepalese economy. This study adopted the descriptive and analytical method. It was found that remittance has increased their household economic and social indicators after returning from foreign employment. It was found that majority of households improved the conditions of housing, provided good education of their children, improved the health of their family members. Moreover, they have started to wear good clothes and increased the savings. It has been concluded that the economic and social condition of all families who have involved in foreign employment have been increased. It was in both aspects i.e. economic as well as social. This study has been carried out to analyze the role of foreign remittance in rural poverty reduction of the study area.

The study applies descriptive analysis; using frequency distribution table and GINI test the study finds that international remittances substantially reduce the level, depth and severity of poverty

Keywords

Remittance, Foreign Workers, Poverty Reduction, Export

Introduction

Foreign remittances can be defined as a transfer of money from a migrant earner (employee/employer or business owner in host country) to their families or other individuals in their home countries. The volume of foreign remittances to developing countries has augmented rapidly over the past decades. IMF estimates that

foreign remittance inflows have grown five-fold in the past three decades and its reach to the US \$ 91 billion in total in 2013. The sum of foreign remittances has been the largest money inflows to developing countries in comparison to foreign direct investment, official development assistance and private financial flows. Foreign remittances are expected to reduce poverty, as they are, in many cases, directly received by the poor, augmenting their income and alleviating their poverty. In Nepal, foreign remittances may make up between 20-30 per cent of the recipient's total household income. They also represent a more stable source of poverty reduction than other capital flows. Flows can last for one generation or more, and usually go to more or less the same family members. As a result of increasing migration, foreign remittances have come more and more into focus as a contributor to development and poverty reduction in Nepal. Recent analysis demonstrates that an increase in international migration is positively linked to a decline in the number of people in poverty. Some studies indicate that a 10 per cent increase in the share of foreign remittances in a country's GDP leads to, on average, a decline from 1.6 to 3.5 per cent in the proportion of people in poverty. Recent evidence indicates that the effect on reducing the poverty gap could in some cases be more important than the effect on the poverty rate. A recent study done by UNCTAD provides additional evidence on the linkage between foreign remittances and poverty reduction in developing countries like Nepal.

The way in which foreign remittances are used can produce wide multiplier effects in the reduction of poverty. While there are differences among countries on how foreign remittances are spent, evidence shows some similarities in the order of priorities among the recipient families and sending migrants. Household consumption represents 70 per cent of the amounts transferred. Then it strongly assists to increase their living standards and as well as the reduction of poverty. They used those transferred foreign remittances for their purposes such as, savings and small investments. Long term household requirements (house building, loan payments, and inputs for family self-sustained agriculture activities). To obtain health and educational facilities (medical services, studies and insurance). To purchase home comfortable items (telephone services, home appliances, furniture and transport), direct household consumptions (water, electricity, and food). Foreign remittance receiving households spend more money on consumption than non-foreign remittance receiving households. However, since foreign remittance receiving households often have a larger income in total it should be expected that their consumption would be higher. Accordingly, it is important to compare the difference in proportions of the spending patterns between foreign remittance receiving and non-foreign remittance receiving households when studying the impacts of foreign remittances. Indirectly it highlights, it has an effect to reduce the poverty level of the country or else improve their standard of living.

1.2 Research Background

Geographical Background of the Study Area

Manthali is a municipality and the headquarter of Ramechhap District in Province No. 3 of Nepal that was established on 2 December 2014 by merging the former Village development-committees Old-Manthali, Bhatauli, Chisapani, Kathjor, Maluwajor, Salupatiand Sunarpani. It was declared the headquarters

of the district in 9 March 1989 (26 Falgun 2045 BS). It lies on the bank of Tamakoshi River. At the time of the 2011 Nepal census it had a population of 454,000 people living in 28,252 individual households.

The ethnic groups of this study area constitute Brahmin, Chhetri, Magar, Gurung, Kami, Damai, Sarki and Majhi etc. according to the CBS census 2011. About 76.4 percent of the total population of this Municipality are literate of that 69.9 % is female and 82.2% is male Here most of the people are engaged in the farming and rest are engaged on other occupations such as business, government jobs, foreign labor, local labor, student etc. which are categorized in non-agriculture sector of occupation. Agriculture is the main occupation of the people of Manthali. The main crops are paddy, millet, wheat, maize, potatoes, and vegetables etc. and the domestic animals are Buffalo, cow, goat, sheep, and poultry, etc.

Remittance Scenario in Nepal

Remittance flows to low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) increased by an estimated 8.5 percent in 2017, to reach \$466 billion (UNDESA 2018). This was a new record. In some countries remittances comprised a large percentage of the national GDP.

In its latest Macroeconomic Report, Nepal Rastra Bank (NRB) said the country's remittance earnings saw a 7.3 percent rise to Rs 679.73 billion in the first eleven months of the fiscal year 2017-18.

In this present situation of Nepalese economy, remittance provides not only the significant portion of the GDP but it also contributes in savings and investment. According to the World Bank's Migration and Remittances Fact book 2016 report, Nepal has been featuring among the top remittance recipient countries over the last three years.

Nepal is third among the countries receiving the highest proportion of remittance in terms of GDP with the country receiving remittance worth 29% of GDP in 2015, according to a report by World Bank. Nepal was fifth in the list in 2011. Remittances in FY 2015/16 contributed around \$6.6 billion a year to Nepal's annual income, up from just \$50m in the mid-1990s, and equivalent to almost more than a quarter of GDP. In fact, the figure is probably substantially higher as remittances are routinely underestimated; the rule of thumb is to add 40% to the official figures. Not all money is sent through legal / verifiable sources. According to World Bank figures, extreme poverty has declined from almost 70% to 25% in the last 15 years, and the extra billions arriving direct to Nepalese households during this period are undoubtedly part of the story, along with large-scale state investment in social sectors and infrastructure.

[Khadka \(2010\)](#) states that in Nepal, remittance is contributing effectively in reducing poverty at rural areas where there are minimum opportunities to earn and get jobs. But due to the lack of proper government policy to encourage the remittance income in the productive sectors; almost 80 percent of the remittance money is used in the unproductive sectors like house building, land buying and other luxurious goods and gadgets. He further states that people usually go outside of the country to have better earnings that will contribute to reducing poverty of rural areas.

Nepal Rastra Bank, the central bank of Nepal publishes data related to remittances continuously. The growth

of the remittances shows that the convertible foreign exchange grew from Rs. 55939.8 million in 1998/99 to Rs. 314391.9 million in 2008/09 which about 5.62 times more. Similarly remittance increase 32.16 times. It is only the money sent through the official agencies (formal channels). According to the current data of World Bank, Nepal's remittance contribution to GDP is in increasing order. From an economic point of view, the economy of the country is also be borne by remittance as 29.0 GDP is being contributed by the remittance which is indeed the good part.

Research Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to analyze the role of remittance in rural poverty reduction of the study area. Besides this, the specific objectives of this study are as follows:

To examine general poverty scenario of the study area.

To analyze the nature and extent of remittance income in the study area.

To gauge the impact of emigration on poverty reduction of the study area.

To find out how remittance change (before and after) on their socioeconomic status.

Literature of review

Different institutions i.e. CEDA, CENAS, NPC, NEW ERA, CBS as well as other independent scholars, have performed their researches on migration. Various emigrational aspects have been studied mostly the causes, effects pattern, distinction, characteristics, problems, etc. All those confine it to the migrant. The utilization of remittance and its effects in rural development have not been studied. Thus, availability of literature referring to Nepal; in this regard is almost absent. It does not mean that there is nothing available about the scenes behind the migrant but these are not directly concerned with the problem. In this respect, some sample studies have been done in some Asian countries which are put here for review.

In a study conducted by [IMF \(2005\)](#) regarding the impact of remittances on growth over an extended period (1970-2003) for 101 developing countries found no statistical link between remittances and per capita output growth, or between remittances and other variables such as education or investment rates. However, this inconclusive result attributed to measurement difficulties arising from the fact that remittances may behave countercyclical with respect to growth.

[Pant \(2006\)](#) explored remittance inflows to Nepal: Economic impact and policy options. The remittances have been an important avenue of support for family members remaining at home. As the number of workers going abroad for employment continues to rise, the corresponding growth of remittances has become a critical flow of foreign currency into Nepal. This has been partly the result of measures undertaken by the concerned officials to streamline financial systems, dismantling controls and creating incentives, with the aim of attracting remittances particularly through the official channels. Economic growth, interest rate and exchange rate policies are crucial determinants of remittance inflows. In order to further encourage the inflow of remittances to the country through official channels, and to promote the tendency to exchange these

remittances of foreign exchange into local currency, it is imperative that these policies be conducive to the inflow of remittances.

[Shrestha \(2008\)](#) has analyzed the contribution of foreign employment and remittances to Nepalese economy. He concluded that remittances sent by the migrant workers are an effective tool for poverty reduction. Though foreign employment is boon to the economy, the facilities are inadequate to back up the increasing trend of migration. The government should play proactive role to promote foreign employment by inducting and adhering to the policy of economic diplomacy.

[Karagoz \(2009\)](#) has made an empirical research on the remittances and economic growth in the case of Turkey. The study showed that remittance flow has statistically meaningful but negative impact on growth. On the other hand, exports and domestic investments positively affect the economic growth, while foreign direct investment has no meaningful affect. Turkey which met with regular and massive labor migration to abroad after 1960s, is still one of the most remittance gain countries in the world.

[Owiafe \(2008\)](#) analyzed the impact of external remittances on poverty reduction in Ghana. The study employed mainly secondary microeconomic time series data analysis. All data were taken from LMF, international financial statistics government, finance statistics and the World Bank and the state of Ghanaian economy. Data were analyzed descriptively and quantitatively. Charts such as trend graphs and table were employed to add in the descriptive analysis. This study adopt newly developed auto regressive distributed lag econometric model.

The study concluded that remittance has indirect impact on economic growth through human capital development and the case of capital constraints, its direct impact is nil, where poverty is concerned remittances seem to have direct impact on poverty reduction, though the direct increase in the income of the poor, thus smoothening household consumption and eating capital constraints.

[Azam and Khan \(2011\)](#) has empirical analyzed the impacts of workers' remittances on economic growth of Azerbaijan and Armenia's economies. The statistical analysis has been made through simple log linear regression model and the method of least square has been used. The study concluded that worker remittances are significant and have positive impacts on economic growth and development. The findings suggested that the relevant authorities of both the countries need to formulate appropriate policies in order to encourage worker remittances and such remittances must be utilized more efficiently.

[Pant \(2011\)](#) explored the harnessing remittances for productive use in Nepal. He concluded that remittances contribute largely to the national economy. The remittances sent home by the migrants affect development at both the household and national levels. At the household level, remittances help to reduce poverty, improve standard of living and attain higher educational levels. At the macro level, remittances could be used for entrepreneurship and productive investment which in turn increases job opportunities and income of the people. Remittance inflows help to augment foreign exchange reserves and improve the current account position.

Adams (2004) used the survey data for Guatemala and Ghana to investigate the effect of remittance from domestic and international migrant on poverty and income distribution. Using both cross section data from Ghana living standard survey and pseudo-panel estimation it is found that international remittances decrease the probability of family being poor. The effect of international remittance in reducing poverty is far higher than effect of domestic remittances in reducing poverty. It concludes that remittances reduce poverty but has no effect on income distribution in Guatemala and Ghana. The degree to which remittances impact poverty depends on how measures poverty.

The study of the literature further reveals that theoretical and empirical evidences on the impact of workers' remittances on economic development and growth have made the issue debatable because some researchers are in favor of remittances positive impacts while some negate its outcomes but a few are of the view that there are no relations between the two. However, comparatively the major portion of literature found is in favor of positive impact of workers' remittances on economic growth and development of developing countries.

Materials and methods

This study is based on primary data from the study area, which I have collected through questionnaire method. So the methodology of this study is descriptive as well as analytical method. It was a micro level study. It is a study survey. The main objective of this study was to review the role of remittance in rural poverty reduction. For this purpose, US \$1 income per day concept was adopted to measure the poverty of the study area. However, I have used the Gini index, a widely used measure, to measure income inequality after and before the remittance of the sample households.

Data Collection Method

This study conducted with primary as well as secondary data. The primary data collected using the questionnaire methods. The survey method confined to the remittance household survey only. A total 300 households were randomly selected. The surveyed area is poor and remote. The survey contained 300 households with complete information. In total 350 questionnaires were issued and distributed for this survey out of which 300 households were interviewed between January and March 2019. The collected data has been processed according to the need of study. The households questionnaire collect information on household demographic composition, housing, access to facilities, expenditure, land, assets holding, education, health, employment, farming and livestock, credit and savings, remittance transfers etc. In the context of secondary data, available sources, like policy document, article, books, web-site have also been used which efforts are already done in the past.

Sampling Design

There are 2018 households and total population is 7569 in Manthali - 1. Among them the working age population is only 2148 (the Population aged between 15 years to 60 years is categorized into the working age population). Among the total no of households total of 400 households were migrated to another place in the

year 2073/74 BS. Among the total population about 20 percent of the people were migrated to another place. Among them about 36.3 percent of people were migrated for their further studies and about 43.7 percent of people were migrated for work. From 2018 total households in the study area, 300 households were selected using proportional size with random sampling method. In order to make the study meaningful as well as short in the limited time period a larger sample size was not feasible. The sample was more than 10 percent of total households, which can be considered as the representative of the universe of study. This survey was conducted from Jun, 2021 to August 2021.

Data Analysis

The data collected from the respondents are presented, analyzed and interpreted. The frequency tables and figures are used to portray the data. Data analysis was done with the help of require tools and techniques. In data analysis the simple technique was used to analysis the result. The data were entered on Excel 2010 of Microsoft. Tables are extensively used to analyze the data.

ANALYSIS AND PRESENTION OF SAMPLED DATA

This chapter deals with the detail analysis and interpretation of primary data collection through questionnaire distributed to the respondent families who collect remittance from abroad. In other words, this chapter deals with all the data related to the topic which are collected in the field survey.

Average Family size, Age, Marital status and Literacy rate of different ethnic groups of sampled households

Caste/Ethnic Group	No. of Respondents	Average family Size	Percent of married	Percent of literate
Chhetri	114	5.13	61.3	92.8
Bhramin	81	4.81	58.2	100
Gurung	30	5.1	71.3	80.3
Kami	21	4.28	80.7	60.2
Magar	18	5.5	70.5	75.6
Sarki	15	7	83.2	62.5
Others	21	5.57	78.6	76.9
Total	300	5.34	71.97	80

Source: Field survey, 2021

Above table shows that among workers seeking foreign employment from Manthali is mostly dominated by Chhetri, Brahmin and Gurung. Comparing the age of the migrant of the three casts with other castes, the average age of the migrant of these castes is very high while other casts like Sarki, Kami has very low average age of the migrant workers.

Sources of Income of the Sampled Households

S.No.	Sources of Income	Number Of Households	Percentage
1	Agriculture	171	40.83
2	Business	99	23.56
3	Jobs	53	12.57
4	Foreign Employment	70	16.75
5	Others	26	6.29
6	Total	419	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

(Note: Due to multiple answers the total no of sample households is more than 100)

The above table presents the income sources of the respondents of the sample area. From that table we can find that most of the family depends on the Agriculture, the second largest sources of income are Business whereas the third largest source of income is Foreign Employment.

Economic Condition of Different Ethnic Groups of Respondents

Caste/Ethnic group	No. of Respondent	Lower Income Group	Medium low Income Group	Medium Income Group	Higher Income Group
Chhetri/Bhrami	195	48	63	51	33
n					
Gurung	30	6	3	12	9
Kami	21	15	3	3	-
Magar	18	12	3	3	-
Sarki	15	15	0	0	-
Others	21	12	6	3	
Total	300	108	78	72	42

Source: Field survey, 2021

From the above table we can see that among the sample households most of the households are Brahmin and Chhetri, where they are quite strong economic background i.e. 33 household from total of 195 households are from high-income group whereas 51 households are from medium income group, 63 households are from medium-low-income group, and only 48 households are in the lowest income group.

Causes of Seeking Foreign Employment from Sampled Households

Caste/Ethnic group	No. of Respondents	Unemployment	Family Debt	Conflict	Earn Money
Chetri/Bhrami	65 195	189	71	32	69
n					

Gurung	30	30	9	6	12
Kami	21	15	21	0	6
Magar	18	14	9	6	6
Sarki	15	15	12	0	3
Others	21	18	12	0	18
Total	300	281	134	46	114

Source: Field survey, 2021

(Note: Due to the multiple answers the total will be more than 100 percent).

Above table shows that unemployment is the main cause of foreign employment for all the castes and ethnic groups.

Range of Costs for Foreign Employment By different Ethnic group

Rs; in thousand

Caste/Ethnic Group	No of Respondents	Average cost (in Rs. 000)	Minimum	Maximum
Chetri/Bhramin	195	90	5	189
Gurung	30	88.5	20	150
Kami	21	8	2	60
Magar	18	49.5	10	95
Sarki	15	12	1.5	80
Others	21	52	20	120
Total	300	50		

Source: Field survey, 2021

Table 4.1.5 shows that the highest cost of 90 thousand for foreign employment is paid by Chhetri/Bhramin. Secondly Gurung also had paid 88.5 thousand. After that Magar and Other castes had paid an average of around 50 thousand for the foreign employment.

Source of Financing of Cost of Foreign Employment for Different Ethnic Groups of Sampled Households

Caste/Ethnic Group	No. of Respondents	Loan	Sales of property	Family Saving
Chetri/Bhramin	195	156	-	39
Gurung	30	18	-	12
Kami	21	18	3	-
Magar	18	12	3	3
Sarki	15	15	3	-
Others	21	12	6	3
Total	300	231	15	57

Source: Field survey, 2019

Table shows that 77 percent respondents of the total borrowed loan to pay for the cost of foreign employment. Another 18 percent respondents had paid from their family savings, and only 5 percent respondents had paid to the cost of foreign employment by selling their property.

Types of Jobs Performed and Duration of Stay in Foreign Country of Respondents from Sampled Households

Caste/ Ethnic Group	No of Respon den ts	Constructio n	Mechanical	Agriculture /Farming	Industrial	Hotel/ Catering	Average Duration of Stay
Chetri/Bh ramin	195	42	81	21	36	15	3yrs
Gurung	30	12	-	-	12	6	3.25yrs
Kami	21	18	-	3	-	-	2.8yrs
Magar	18	9	-	3	6	-	2.7Yrs
Sarki	15	9	-	3	-	3	2.5yrs
Others	21	12	6	-	3	-	2.7yrs
Total	300	102	87	30	57	24	2.8yrs

Source: Field survey, 2021

Table 4.1.7 shows that most of the migrated respondents work in the construction areas in which 34 percent. Most of the people from lower cast work in the construction areas due to lack of other technical knowledge to work in other areas. The second most employed area is Mechanical. The third largest area of employment for the Nepalese workers is Industrial area.

Causes to Return for Foreign Employment for Different Ethnic Group of Respondents

Caste/Ethnic Group	No. of Respondents	Employment Purpose	Conflict	No Plan to go
Chetri/Bhramin	195	126	45	24
Gurung	30	24	3	3
Kami	21	21	-	-
Magar	18	15	-	3
Sarki	15	15	-	-
Others	21	9	3	9
Total	300	210	51	39

Source: Field survey, 2021

The above table shows that because of unemployment problem 70 percent respondent return to foreign

employment.

Income Earned in Abroad for Different Ethnic Group of Respondents

Caste / Ethnic Group	No. of respon dents	Average monthly income (in thousand)							
		Based on destination		Based on skill		Types of job			
		Gulf	Malaysia	Skilled	Unskilled	Mechanic	Hotel	Industry	Agr.
Chetri /Bhrami n	195	15.13	12.4	24	10.5	25	15.5	12.5	8.5
Gurung	30	12.15	12	20	8.75	21	14	10	-
Kami	21	9.83	8.5	17	7.5	18	-	8.5	7.8
Magar	18	9.76	8.5	21	9	14	15	9.5	8.5
Sarki	15	8.5	7.5	18	7	15	11	9	-
Others	21	10.3	9	20	-	18	14	9.5	9.5
total	300	11	9.65	20	8.54	18.5	13.58	9.83	8.5

Source: Field survey, 2021

Above table shows that the respondents who have done the work in Gulf Countries earned more money than the respondents worked in Malaysia. Comparing these two countries the average monthly income of the respondents in Malaysia is Rs.9.65 thousand where the average monthly income in Gulf countries is Rs.11 thousand.

Use of Remittance and the Skills learnt in Foreign Employment

Caste/ Ethnic group	No. of respondent	Household Expenses	Utilization of remittance			Use of Skills	
			Loan payment	Investment (land, share)	Social activities	Yes	No
Chetri/ Bhramin	195	195	141	57	48	36	159
Gurung	30	27	18	6	18	6	24
Kami	21	21	6	-	-	-	21
Magar	18	18	15	6	-	6	12
Sarki	15	15	15	-	-	-	15
Others	21	15	12	9	3	-	21
Total	300	291	207	78	69	48	252

Source: Field survey, 2021

(Note: Due to the multiple answers the total numbers of the households are more than the total number of sample size.)

The above table presents the fact about the utilization of Remittance income as well as the utilization of skills learnt in foreign employment. From it, we can conclude that among all the respondents and their household,

97 percent of the respondents uses their income in the household expenses i.e. in food, cloths, health and the education of their family. 69 percent of the households use their income in loan payment of their family. Only about 26 households are using their income from abroad in investment purpose i.e. for buying land, Home and Shares or establishing industries.

Change in Different Indicators of Respondents Due to Foreign Employment

Indicators	Increased	Decreased	No change	Total
Economic Status	207	24	69	300
Standard of living	171	9	120	300
Social attitude	219	-	81	300
skills	246	-	54	300

Source: Field survey, 2021

The above analysis is not based on the ethnic composition or group but it is based on the total sample size without categorization. It shows that 69 percent of the respondents reported that their Economic Status is increased due to foreign employment. 23 percent of the respondents replied that their economic status is same before and after foreign employment. 8 percent of the respondent's economic status has decreased due to the foreign employment it means they had increased the sum of family debt for the reason of foreign employment.

Impact on Other Household Indicators of the Respondents

Indicators	Increased	Worsened	Same	Total
Condition of house	234	-	66	300
Education of children	207	-	93	300
Health of family member	150	54	96	300
Clothing	222	-	78	300
Cash available with them	111	66	123	300

Source: Field survey, 2021

The above given table shows that 78 percentage of the respondents reported to have improved their condition of housing. It shows that anybody who had returned from foreign employment either have made new house or repaired old house to improve their housing condition.

Sampled household made by different types

S. N.	Types of house	Total number
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1	Made up of rod, concrete and cement	81
2	Made by stone and slate stone roof	132
3	Mud and thatched roof	87
	Total	300

Source: Sample survey 2021

This table shows that, Out of the sampled households, 81 were made up of rod, concrete and cement; 132 were of stone and slate stone roof; and 87 were of mud and thatched roof. It indicates that that most of the sample households have made by stone and slate stone roof.

Educational Status of Sample Households (6 years of age and over)

Educational status	Male		Female		Total population	Total percentage
		percentage		percentage		
Illiterate	38	16.66	67	22.94	105	20.19
Literate	52	22.82	112	38.36	164	31.54
Educated up to high school	95	41.66	91	31.17	186	35.77
Above high school	43	18.86	22	7.53	65	12.5
	228	100	292	100	520	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

The above- table 4.4.1 shows that out of 520 sample population 105 people are illiterate, 164 people are literate, 186 people are educated up to High School level, and 65 people are well educated (Bachelor level and above). In the above table, it is clearly shown that the number of female illiterate is more than the no of male illiterate. Most of the male population is educated above High school level, but most of the female are only literate.

Regular Money Income of the Sample Households

S. N.	Regular monthly income	No. of Households
1	Less than 5000	72
2	5000 – 10000	63
3	10000 – 20000	105
4	20000 - 50000	42
5	Above 50000	18
	Total Households	300

Source: Field survey, 2021

Above Table 4.9.1, presents the fact of the sample households of the study area that about 45 percent of the

total sampled households receive less than NRs.10000 per month. Which means an average of NRs 1650 per month is available to each person of the sample households. This is very below the absolute poverty line. Only 6 percent of the households receive more than50000 per month as the regular income.

Pre and post analysis of remittance

Pre Remittance				Post Remittance		
Ye	No	Total	Particulars	Yes	No	Total
13	165	300	Quality products consumed	235	65	300
10	198	300	Consumption of meat twice a week	224	76	300
11	290	300	Consumption of fruits in a regular basis	240	60	300
63	237	300	Private Vehicles were owned	150	150	300
31	269	300	Investment in luxury items	160	140	300
23	70	300	Children's were enrolled in government	15	285	300
82	218	300	Children's were enrolled in private schools	227	73	300
11	190	300	Higher education facility	270	30	300
90	210	300	Regular health checkups	180	120	300
95	205	300	Can afford doctors as when required	210	90	300
30	270	300	Invested on life insurances	140	160	300
10	290	300	Go out for dinner once or more than a week	95	205	300
10	200	300	Engage in socialization programs	180	120	300
10	290	300	Watch movies in cinema halls	98	202	300
75	225	300	Savings made	180	120	300
15	145	300	Loan taken	243	57	300
40	260	300	Paid the loan to some extent or full	180	120	300
23	277	300	Investment in new business	102	198	300
28	272	300	Made a new house or reconstructed the old one	196	104	300
29	269	300	Children's health erosion due to excess money	83	217	300

Source field survey, 2021

From the above table we can see that there has been a huge impact of remittance in the households before it was generated and after it is generated. We can clearly see that there have been changes in the expenditure pattern of the households. 100 households who didn't consume quality products before they started to consume quality products after the remittance were received.

Income with and Without Remittance of the respondents

It was also tried to figure out the ratio of income of the individual with and without remittance. Through this analysis, Gini coefficient was tried to identify so that income distribution in terms of inequality could be assessed.

The Gini coefficient is usually defined mathematically based on the Lorenz curve which plots the proportion of the total income of the population (Y axis) that is cumulatively earned by the bottom X of the population. The line at 45 degrees thus represents perfect equality of incomes. The Gini coefficient can then be thought of as the ratio of the area that lies between the line of equality and the Lorenz curve over the total area under the line of equality i.e., $G = A/(A + B)$. It is also equal to $2A$ and to $1 - 2B$ due to the fact that $A + B = 0.5$ (since the axes scale from 0 to 1). If all people have non-negative income (or wealth, as the case may be), the Gini coefficient can theoretically range from 0 (complete equality) to 1 (complete inequality); it is sometimes expressed as a percentage ranging between 0 and 100. In practice, both extreme values are not quite reached.

Graphical Representation of the Gini Index of the study

Equality = equality line

Lorenz 1 = income distribution after the remittance, which is more equality than Lorenz curve 2

Lorenz 2 = income distribution before remittance, which is more inequality.

The value of Gini Coefficient for the distribution on total income (with remittance):

Area

$A = 0.180599$

Gini = 0.361197

The value of Gini coefficient is 0.361197, that means the income distribution with remittance is minimally unequal.

The value of Gini Coefficient for the distribution on income without remittance:

Area

$$A = 0.221964$$

$$\text{Gini} = 0.443927$$

Here, the value of Gini coefficient is 0.443927, that means the income distribution without remittance is unequal but moderately.

Findings

When we compare the value of Gini with remittance and without remittance, the value of Gini without remittance is higher (0.443927) than the Gini value with remittance (0.361197). So, there is high inequality when there is no remittance contribution whereas there is comparatively low inequality when there is the contribution of remittance. Thus, we can conclude that the remittance has a contribution in reducing inequality in the selected area as Manthali -1, meaning remittance does not contribute to greater income inequality rather it contributes to reducing income inequality.

Discussions & Conclusion

The role of remittance in rural poverty reduction has been tested using primary data of sampled households. The result of GINI coefficient suggests that there has been changed in income distribution of the study area. Therefore, we can conclude that there is a role of remittance in rural poverty reduction. There has been significant rise of migration of young population from Nepal in the recent years. Such emigration resulted to a sharp rise in remittance inflow exceeding all other source of foreign currency income. Remittance inflow helps to provide person - to person aid especially to the poor people who reside at the rural part of Nepal. Poverty is the major burning issue in the under development and developing nations in this present ere. Nepal being a small landlocked and agricultural country is suffering from a major problem of poverty. If one concentrates on the poverty situation of our country its magnitude is very large, people are not getting their minimum requirements. Due to the various factors like unemployment, increasing population, political instability and internal conflict. Many youths are lured to go abroad for employment Remittance income has been helping in the reduction of rural poverty but due to the lack of proper government policies remittance income is being used up in various unproductive sectors.

It is clearly shown that the national GDP growth rate is directly related to the various factors like total saving of the economy and total investment of the economy. On the other hand, saving is determined by the investment, without investment, the country cannot get higher GDP growth rate. The investment in the country like Nepal is directly dependent on the remittance invested into the economy. Therefore, we can say that the remittance is the major factors of development of country like Nepal. There is gap between saving and investment, thus utilization of remittance in investment is a great need of today e.g., development process etc., in the world economy, 47 remittance plays vital role and in the development countries it has its own value. Going further the economy of these countries has been gradually changing into remittance economy.

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